

Full Scale Structural Experimental Investigation of an E-glass/Epoxy Composite

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SUMMARY: Structural test of a new wind turbine rotor blade was performed to evaluate design uncertainties due to material defects, analytical assumptions and production process, and quantify their effect on its structural integrity.

In the full-scale static strength test, the measuring parameters were the blade weight, location of center of gravity, in-plane strains, deflections and failure loads. Performing a three-point bending test of the full-scale (size) blade simulated the aerodynamic load experienced by the rotor blade. Analytical predictions for mass of the blade, center of gravity location, blade tip deflection and the first flap-wise natural frequency were in good agreement with the measured values. The difference was less than 4%, indicating that the blade response was accurately modeled by a linear analysis. The axial strain of the blade skin was also measured at several blade stations: 5.56m, 11.59m and 13.43m at an applied load of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% of the maximum design load. Acceptable agreement was achieved between experimental and theoretical strain results, using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion.

KEYWORDS: Composite wind turbine blade, Full-scale structural test, Fatigue Life

INTRODUCTION

The fast progress in wind energy technology and wide spread usage of wind turbines require a standardization of the wind turbine main components aiming at a further cost reduction. This is related not only to large volume production and standardization of production methods but also material test methods and design rules [1-2].

In South Korea, since the introduction of the “New and Renewable Source of Energy (NRSE) Development & Promotion Act” in 1987, the Korean government has invested considerably on the development of a new wind turbine system. One of these initiatives resulted in the design and manufacturing of an E-glass/epoxy composite blade for a 750KW medium-scale horizontal axis wind turbine system (HAWTS) [3]. The first author and his co-workers have contributed considerably to the structural design and analysis, manufacturing and structural testing of this medium scale composite blade [4-8].

The blades of a wind turbine rotor are generally regarded as the most critical components of the wind turbine system. Therefore, careful structural tests of the full-size structure are required to evaluate the effect of material defects, imperfections introduced during the manufacturing process and assumptions used in the design and analysis of the component. Of course, tests at the specimen and sub-component level are also required in order to gain confidence in the design process and reduce the number of costly full-size experiments [9]. Mayer [9] showed various test examples such as specimen tests, component tests for the spar, the blade root joint and the T-bolt root attachment and full-scale tests, characterizing static and fatigue behaviors. Delft et al. [11] carried out the full-scale fatigue test of a laminated wood-epoxy blade for a 500KW wind turbine. Also, Inomata et al. [12] tested and presented operating stress results for the blade of a prototype 500KW-wind turbine developed by the NEDO in Tappi Wind Park in Japan.

Usually, the majority of tests are performed at coupon level where different types of loading can be applied (static and dynamic) taking into account hygro-thermal effects that may influence the response of the composite structure. This also enables the investigator to study different types of materials and laminated configurations using standard test methods and test machines at much lower

cost. However, even though the full-scale test is quite expensive, the test must be performed in order to verify the design and manufacturing procedure and gain confidence of the blade's structural integrity when in service. The full-scale test of a blade is performed under static and fatigue loading conditions. Currently the IEC 61400-23/CDV test regulation [10] is used as a guideline for the full-scale structural testing that gives guidance for interpretation and evaluation of results.

In this study, the full-scale static test of a new medium class E- glass/epoxy wind turbine blade is described and strain results at different applied loads are presented. These will be used in the near future in the qualification process of the blade and the whole wind turbine system.

DESIGN SUMMARY

In the present design, the blade has a skin-spar-foam sandwich construction with span length of 23.3m, maximum chord length of 2.1m, tip chord length of 0.5m and hub twisting angle of 12°. For simplicity, it has no coning angle and no blade-to-shaft hinge, but has a full active pitch control to reduce cyclic aerodynamic loads. The blade is manufactured with a straight leading edge and the straight and tapered trailing edge for ease of construction and the modified thick NACA 63-xxx airfoil is used at the blade root for good structural performance. For weight reduction, an insert bolt type joint structure is introduced, resulting in a smooth geometry and low local stress concentration. Provision for lightning strike protection is made and round blade tip to minimize wake effect and noise. An appropriate gel coat is applied to the blade to minimize aerodynamic drag, penetration of humidity and solar deterioration. The proposed cross-sectional configuration at the root of the blade is similar to that of reference [9,13].

In operation, the wind turbine may experience different loads such as aerodynamic and inertial loads, loads due to accumulation of ice, hydro-thermal and mechanical loads. A cell-box type with a skin-spar-foam sandwich construction was thought to sustain these complex loads quite effectively. The spar flange is manufactured using unidirectional E-glass/epoxy tape; the two spar webs are of a sandwich construction with a urethane foam core and a $\pm 45^\circ$ -fabric skin, similar to the construction of the outer sandwich shell of the blade. The E-glass/epoxy composite material was chosen because of low cost, appropriate fatigue lifetime, desirable specific strength and stiffness and ease of manufacture. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of materials used [14].

Structural design requirements such as the minimum clearance limits between the blade tip and the tower wall, the strain limits along the fiber direction, the surface stress limit and fatigue life time over 20 years, were specified by the design requirements of the Germanischer-Lloyd (GL) regulations [15].

Table 1 Material properties [14]

Material Property	UD Tape-GFRP	Fabric-GFRP ply properties	Urethane Foam
E_1 (N/mm ²)	35700	22147	60.86
E_2 (N/mm ²)	10600	2658	59.86
G_{12} (N/mm ²)	2810	1617	19.18
ν_{12}	0.324	0.3	0.2
X_t (N/mm ²)	711.0	367.3	2.63
X_c (N/mm ²)	1200.0	411.0	1.41
Y_t (N/mm ²)	38.0	40.0	2.49
Y_c (N/mm ²)	183.0	141.0	1.41
S (N/mm ²)	65.7	52.8	0.71

ρ (g/cm ³)	1.80	1.87	0.1197
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Various design load cases including aerodynamic, centrifugal, gravitational, thermal and ice loads and operating conditions such as stand-by, start up, power production and shut-down due to faults were analyzed and compared with GL Regulations for the certification of wind energy conversion systems[15].

In the current design approach, the optimal blade structural configuration was determined through a parametric study using a finite element method . The skin thickness, thickness and width of the spar flange and thickness, location and length of the front and rear spar web were varied until design criteria were satisfied.

The finite element program used for the structural analysis is a well-known commercial code NISA II (Numerically Integrated Element for System Analysis) [23]. The element types used for the static stress analysis are the 3-D laminated composite shell element and the 3-D laminated sandwich element with 12 nodes. In this investigation, it is shown that the most dominant design parameters are: the thickness of the spar flange and skin for weight reasons, the thickness of the spar flange and the location of the front and rear spar web for sustaining maximum stress and/or strain, the thickness and the width of the spar flange for the blade tip clearance and the location of the front spar web for minimizing the distortion angle. Performing the linear static stress analysis, modal analysis, buckling analysis and additional stress analysis related to ice and thermal loading, it was confirmed that the blade structure is safe and stable operating under the various load cases described above. The blade root joint with the insert bolts is a new design concept. It was also proved by the finite element stress analysis that the joint is safe against the design load and fatigue loading conditions. Figures 1 to 3 show detailed dimensions at root, middle and tip of the blade. Table 2 presents the stress analysis results of four design load cases, which are the rated wind speed condition of 12.5m/s(load case 1), the rated wind speed plus the extreme gust condition of 9m/s(load case 2), the cut out wind speed of 25m/s plus the extreme gust condition(load case 3), and the stationary limit load condition in storm of 55m/s(load case 4). Load cases 1 to 3 are considered in wind direction changes between -40 to +40 degrees at maximum rotational wind speed of 35 rpm in operation. Fig. 4 shows the stress contours of σ_{11} along the fiber direction developed in the 1st ply ($\pm 45^\circ$) of the skin during the design load case 2.

Fig. 1 Cross-section of the blade at 0.286R station

Fig. 2 Cross-section of the blade at 0.598R station

Fig. 3 Cross-section of the blade at .0R station

Fig. 4 σ_{11} (fiber direction) stress contours in the 1st ply of the .0R station $\pm 45^\circ$ skin (design load case 2).

As shown in Fig. 4, the blade structure satisfies the design criteria such as blade tip clearance limit from the tower wall of 50% in operation, relatively to stationary, strain limit of 0.25% in compression and 0.35% in tension and strength safety factor of 2.7.

Table 3 presents the results of the modal analysis that calculates natural frequencies for the first and second flap-wise and chord-wise bending modes and the first twisting mode. In this investigation, it was found that there is no resonance between the blade itself and excitation loadings. The buckling load factors for the first to the fifth buckling modes of the blade are shown in Table 4. The most important buckling mode is the first mode (the critical mode) and its load safety factor is 3.43.

Fatigue life for operating more than 20 years was estimated by using the S-N linear damage equation, Goodman diagrams, the load spectrum and Spera's empirical formulae[16]. By this method, a dynamic structural problem for fatigue of the blade can be converted into a static structural design problem [9, 16-20]. According to this analysis, the maximum tensile and compressive stresses developed in the blade due to cyclic loads were 62.87MPa and -55.19MPa, respectively. Allowable fatigue stresses are 180.74MPa for tensile stress and 302MPa for compressive stress. Since the safety factors for the allowable fatigue stresses are 3.5 for tensile and 6.6 for compressive, the designed wind turbine blade satisfies the design criteria for a fatigue life of 20 years.

Table 2 Results of linear static stress analysis

Load cases		Ccase1	Ccase2	Ccase3	Ccase4	
Max [Mpa]	Skin (1 st ply)	x=0.811, y=12.76	-16.4	-22.6	-23.8	-14.6
		x=0.797, y=13.10	18.2	24.3	26.9	14.7
	Spar (15 th ply)	x=0.642, y=13.10	-53.0	-74.9	-82.1	-39.7
		x=0.466, y=13.10	73.5	97.6	105.3	63.1
Max. tip deflection (m)		1.21	1.64	1.77	1.03	
Clearance from tower		69%	57%	55%	74 %	
Safety Factor (Tsai-Wu failure criterion)		4.6	3.5	3.0	7.1	
Max. strain [%] in fiber direction	Tension	0.23	0.31	0.34	0.19	
	Comp.	0.16	0.23	0.25	0.13	

Where x = length from the leading edge [m], y = length from the root [m] (- : compressive , + : tensile)

Table 3 Results of modal analysis

Mode shape	Natural frequency(Hz)
First flap-wise bending (F-1)	1.856
First chord-wise bending (L-1)	2.034
Second flap-wise bending (F-2)	5.280
Second chord-wise bending (L-2)	6.610
First torsional (T-1)	18.08
First tower bending (TB-1)	0.659

Table 4 Buckling load factors

Mode shape	Load factor
1 st mode	3.43
2 nd mode	3.54
3 rd mode	4.28
4 th mode	4.39
5 th mode	4.60

MANUFACTURING

Two manufacturing processes were used, i.e., the contact molding[9] for the spar webs, which the dry reinforced fiber is laid up on a mold and is then impregnated with resin and consolidated, and the prepreg molding to the skins and the spar flanges, which the impregnated UD tapes or fabrics is laid up on a mold and consolidated with a proper temperature and pressure. Before manufacturing the blade, the molds should be

manufactured. In this study, the master molds for the GFRP molds are made of wood. The whole length of the master mold for the blade is divided into eight pieces, and each piece is manufactured by lots of blade profile templates. And then the surface of the assembled master mold is well polished and then coated by a Gel coat. The manufacturing molds are fabricated by laying-up the GFRP fabric prepregs on the master mold with proper stiffeners. Fig. 5 shows a view of lower part of the blade about laying-up foam cores for the skin, and Fig. 6 shows insert bolts in assembling at the root of blade.

Fig. 5 Laying-up foam cores for the skin sandwich on lower part mold of the blade

Fig. 6 Insert bushings and bolts in the blade root with a fixture

The test procedure used for the static strength test is shown in Fig. 7. In the full-scale static test, the measured parameters were the weight, center of gravity, applied load, displacements and axial strains. Table 5 indicates the test equipment and measuring sensors used for collecting data during the static loading test.

Fig. 7 Procedure of the static strength test

Table 5 Equipment and sensors used in the static strength test

Name of Sensor equipment	Measured Parameter	Type & specification
Strain gauge	Strain	CEA-00-250 UW-120
Load cell	Load	5000-DSCK, 5 tonf, 3ea.
Displacement transducer	Displacement	PT-101-0100, 5ea.
Data acquisition system	Data acquisition	System 4000, AI1600, 40 channels

In this static loading test, the load case 1 is discussed. As mentioned earlier, this load case includes the aerodynamic load at the rated wind speed reached in practical operation including wind direction change and gust. Moreover this load will be used for the qualification test of the final full-size blades to be mass-produced.

In order to simulate the aerodynamic load, the three-point loading method is applied. Fig. 8 shows the simulated flap-wise bending moment distribution when three concentrated loads are applied at points located

17.1m(point 1), 20.26m(point 2) and 21.85m(point 3) from the blade root. The load values at these positions along the blade length are shown in Table 6.

Fig. 8 Bending moment distribution (flap-wise test)

Fig. 9 Full-size blade under lateral loading

modulus are strongly dependent on the fiber volume fraction, so these values were adjusted using the following conversion factor[21,22];

$$r_f = \frac{V_{fa}}{V_{fr}} \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

where, V_{fa} is the actual fiber volume fraction and V_{fr} is the reference one (60%). Other material properties (E_2 , G_{12} , ν_{12}) are less affected by V_f so are not corrected in the finite element calculation. Table 7 shows both measured and predicted results for mass of the blade, location of center of gravity(spanwise), tip deflection and the first flap-wise natural frequency. The difference is between 2.0 and 4%.

Fig.10 and Table 8 present the measured and predicted deflections at the maximum thickness of the blade profile along the spanwise stations when the maximum design load is applied. There is a small difference between the measured and predicted results when the reference fiber volume fraction of 60% is used in the analysis. However, a good agreement is achieved when the actual fiber volume fraction of 52.5% is employed, Table 8.

Table 6 Maximum design loads for the static strength test (load case 1)

Loading points (m)	17.1	20.6	21.85
Loads (kN)	27.44	17.64	9.8
Measuring range for strain gages(m)	4 ~ 15		

Fig. 9 illustrates the deflected blade under bending (three point concentrated loads are applied).

COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASURED AND PREDICTED

A prototype E-glass/epoxy blade was tested statically and results used for comparison with the analytical model based on the laminate plate theory and the Tsai-Wu failure criterion. In the bending test of the full-size blade no local failure, debonding, delamination or local buckling were observed up to the maximum design load. The previous manufacturing and testing experiences helped us to perform careful experiments for material characterisation and improve the final manufacturing process, procedures that are now well established in our laboratory. Accurate fiber volume fraction(v_f) measurements are essential in the stress analysis calculations since large variations could result to inaccurate estimates. In coupon tests where specimens obtained from an actual blade, their average fiber volume fraction was 52.5%, compared to 60% suggested by the materials manufacturer. Axial strength and

Table 7 Measured and predicted values of the blade

	Mass of blade(kg)	Spanwise center of mass (m)	Tip deflection (mm)	Flap-wise 1 st N.F. (Hz)

Measured	2951	8.451	1978.6	1.820
Predicted	2883	8.786	1921.0	1.856
Error (%)	2.36	3.81	3.0	2.0

Fig. 10 Comparison between measured and predicted deflections along the blade at maximum design load

Table 8 Comparison between measured and predicted deflections along the blade at maximum design load

Distance from root[m]	Measured deflection [mm]	Predicted deflection at V_f : 52.5% [mm]
15	525.6	470.9
17	809	737.3
18.13	1012.6	892.1
19.97	1331.9	1215
23.9	1978.6	1921

applied loads. Even though a slightly non-linearity from 80% to 100% of maximum design load is shown, a linear static solution is sufficient for the design purpose, because the amount of non-linearity is relatively small.

Table 9 summarizes the measured and theoretical deflections at blade position $0.67r/R$ (17.0m from the blade root) and the tip of the blade at different

Table 9 Comparison between measured and predicted tip deflection

Measuring Position		Deflection (mm) at different applied loads				
		20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
17.0m	Test	172	336	483	624	809
	$V_f=52.5\%$	152	299	445	591	737
23.9m	Test	447	831	1193	1541	1978
	$V_f=52.5\%$	398	779	1160	1540	1921

Fig.11 and Table 10 show comparisons between measured and predicted strain results for the upper part of the blade. Three different locations at the maximum thickness positions of the blade profile, $0.236r/R$ (5.56m), $0.493r/R$ (11.59m) and $0.574r/R$ (13.43m) are presented when the applied load is 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% of the maximum design load. The theoretical values are well agreed with experimental measurements.

Fig. 11 Comparison between measured and predicted strains on the upper part of the blade.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a structural test of an E-glass/epoxy wind turbine rotor blade was performed to examine design uncertainties due to selected materials, design and analysis methods, coupon test methods and production processes, and to evaluate their possible impact on the structural integrity.

In the full-scale static loading test, the measuring parameters were mass and center of gravity, the first flap-wise natural frequency, and strains and deflections due to different applied loading conditions. In order to simulate the aerodynamic load, the blade was loaded laterally by three concentrated loading. Prediction for mass of the blade, radial center of gravity, blade tip deflection

and the first flap-wise natural frequency from the model was in good agreement with the measured values with an error of less than 4%. Good agreement between the measured and predicted results for deflection was achieved when the actual fiber volume fraction of 52.5%, was used in the analysis. This suggests that properties obtained from small specimens may not represent the values corresponding to the full size component. A small non-linearity in the load-strain response appeared at 80% of the design load (case 1). However, analytical results based on a linear analysis give good predictions, suggesting that for design purposes of the examined blade non-linearity effects are not significant. The present study has contributed significantly into the actual design of the medium scale electricity generating horizontal axis wind turbine system used currently in Korea.

Table 10 Comparison between measured and predicted strains ($\mu\epsilon$) on the upper part of the blade

	5.56m			11.59m			13.43m		
	Test	FEM	Error	Test	FEM	Error	Test	FEM	Error
20%	-57	-45	-21%	-181	-167	-8%	-189	-153	-19%
40%	-163	-141	-13%	-360	-392	9%	-368	-350	-5%
60%	-275	-263	-4%	-522	-577	10%	-537	-550	2%
80%	-323	-369	14%	-655	-755	15%	-687	-730	6%
100%	-428	-482	13%	-878	-966	10%	-896	-940	5%

REFERENCES

1. T. Ackermann, and L. Söder, "Wind Energy Technology and Current Status", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol.4, pp.315-374, 2000.
2. "Windpower Monthly", *Industrial Magazine*, ISSN 0901-7318, Monthly Published since 1985.
3. J. S. Kim, "Renewable Energy Development and Supply in Korea", *Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Energy and Korean Energy Management Corporation*, 2000.
4. C. Kong, J. Bang, and H. Kim, "A Study on Aerodynamic Analysis and Starting Simulation for Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine Blade", *J. of KSPE*, Vol.3, No.3, pp.40-46, 1999.
5. C. Kong and J. Jeong, "Improvement of Design by Structural Test for 750kw HAWT Composite Blade", *J. of KSPE*, Vol.4, No.3, pp.22-29, 2000.
6. C. Kong, J. Jeong, M. Kang and C. Kim, "A Study on Structural Design of Medium Scale Composite Wind Turbine Blade", *International Conference on Advances in Strategic Technologies(ICAST2000)*, pp.1789-1800, 2000.
7. C. Kong, S. Jeong, B. Jang and J. Bang, "Design Improvement on Wind Turbine Blade of Medium Scale HAWT by Considering", *J. of KSPE*, Vol.4, No.3, pp.29-37, 2000.
8. C. Kong, J. Bang, M. Kang, S. Jeong and J. Yoo, "Structural Design of Medium Scale Composite Wind Turbine Blade", *13th International Conference on Composite Materials(ICCM-13)*, 2001.
9. R. M. Mayer, "Design of Composite Structures against Fatigue Applications to Wind Turbine Blades", *Antony Rowe Ltd.*, pp.195-208, 1996.
10. Technical Note: IEC 61400-1 GL Test Regulation, 2000.
11. D. R. V. Delft, D. C. Corbet and J. L. van Leeuwe, "Full Scale Fatigue Tests of Wood-Epoxy Blades", *Amsterdam EWEC'91*, 1991.
12. N. Inomata, K. Tsuchiya and S. Yamada, "Measurement of Stress on Blade of NEDO's 500 kw Prototype Wind Turbine", *Renewable Energy*, Vol.16, pp.912-915, 1999.
13. D. L. E. Gourieres, "Wind Power Plants Theory and Design", *Pergamon Press*, 1982.
14. C. Kong, H. Kim and J. Kim, "A Study on Structural and Aerodynamic Design of Composite Blade for Large Scale HAWT System", *Final Report, Hankuk Fiber Ltd.*, 2000.
15. Germanischer Lloyd, "Regulations for the Certification of Wind Energy Conversion System", *Germanischer Lloyd*, 1999.
16. D. A. Spera, "Dynamic Loads in Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbines Part II : Empirical Equations", *Windpower '93*, pp.282-289, 1993.
17. A. Palmgren, "Die Lebendauer von Kugellagern", *Zeitschrift von Deutche Ingenieurring*, Vol.68, pp.339-341 1924.
18. M. A. Miner, "Cumulative Damage in Fatigue", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol.12, pp.A-

- 159-164 1945.
19. J. F. Mandell, R. M. Reed and D. D. Samborsky, "Fatigue of Fiberglass Wind Turbine Blade Materials", *Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, New Mexico*, SAND92-7005, 1992.
 20. P. S. Veers, C. H. Lange and S. R. Winterstein, "Farow: A Tool for Fatigue and Reliability of Wind Turbines", *Windpower '93*, pp.342-349, 1993.
 21. C. Zweben, H. H. Thomas and T. W. Chou, "Mechanical Behavior and Properties of Composite Materials volume 1", *Technomic Publishing Co., INC.*, 1989.
 22. G. E. Dieter, J. Chapman, H. T. Hahn, D. H. Hodges, C. W. Rogers, L. Valarani and M. D. Zuteck, "Assessment of Research Needs For Wind Turbine Rotor Materials Technology", *National Academy Press, Washington, D.C.*, 1991.
 23. "EMRC, NISAII-User's Manual", version5.2, 1992.

